

From Songs of Innocence to Songs of Experience: The Trajectory of Bengali Popular Music from 1980s to the Present

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Abstract: This article maps the journey of Bengali music from the 1980s, and divides our songs from this period into three main categories, and they are named (somewhat playfully) songs of innocence, songs of transition, and songs of experience. The first phase is identified with 1980s, the second with 1990s and the third phase is identified with 2000s and 2010s.

Keywords: Bengali Modern Songs, Bengali Film Music, Music Industry, Evolution of Bengali Music, Moheener Ghoraguli, Kishore Kumar, Manna Dey, Pulak Bandyopadhyay, Bappi Lahiri, R D Burman, Amit Kumar, Kumar Sanu, Suman Chattopadhyay, Kabir Suman, Nachiketa Chakraborty, Jibonmukhi Bangla Gaan, Anjan Dutt, Shilajit, Chandrabindoo, Fossils, Chandril Bhattacharya, Anindya Chattopadhyay, Upal Sengupta, Rupam Islam, Anupam Roy.

Written language cannot ever do sufficient justice to a performative art like music, a fact that ominously hovers over this academic exercise in the very beginning. Diptiprakash Majumdar in the preface to his *Hajar Bochhorer Bangla Gaan*, an eclectic collection of Bengali songs with notations from *chorjapod* to Bankim's Vande Mataram, observes that the (330 pages long) book is a product of 32 years of live performances by a number of musicians, singers, researchers. That overwhelms us with the mammoth scope of music, and makes us aware of the painful insufficiency of our available format of academic analysis to live up to this art form, which thrives on performance, and not theory. However, that insufficiency notwithstanding, we need to undertake this musicological journey in order to produce a brief outline of Bengali songs from the 1980s to the present.

The main proposition of this article is this: we can categorise Bengali popular music from 1980s till date into three broad parts. First category would be what we (playfully) call the songs of innocence. They are not products of an 'innocent' music industry, in fact the truth is far from that. But their lyrics

have a pretence of innocence. They are mostly the romantic songs, penned by the likes of Pulak Bandyopadhyay, and melodiously sung by singers like Kishore Kumar (Manna Dey, who falls within this category, was relatively inactive during 1980s, and only re-emerged during 1990s, in a re-forged partnership with Pulak Bandyopadhyay). Film and non-film songs of Kumar Sanu and Amit Kumar would also feature in this segment. R D Burman and Bappi Lahiri were two great music composers of this phase, both were based in Bombay. Further, these songs had a format of collaboration, and the lyricist, composer, singer (three separate figures) came together under the aegis of the film producer in this process. They were mainly film songs, and even when a singer did an album of non-film songs, the combination and ambience (including the lyric and composition) that produced film music got replicated. One last point about them is that they bore testimony to a domination of Bollywood over Bengali music industry. These singers we have just named, though they were Bengali, were all based in the Hindi film industry. Hemanta Mukhopadhyay, who was based in Kolkata (albeit his stint in Bollywood as Hemant Kumar during 1950s and 1960s) was largely a spent force throughout the 1980s, before he breathed his last in 1989.

Then, the songs of transition. They still attempt to carry that romantic project (not so much in its innocence as in its rebellion), are now infused with an angst, and a modernist (somewhat frustrated) hope for transformation, betraying often a political zeal. They came in the immediate aftermath of the fall of socialism in eastern Europe and fall of the Soviet, when the left-leaning bhadralok was desperately searching for anchorage. Such songs also become increasingly self-conscious as music, as they emerge in a period when film music suffered a terminal decline in Bengal. They nonetheless try to form a community with other art forms, a fact that distinguishes them from that sense of super-specialisation and commercial reification of music which characterised the songs of the previous phase. Songs of Suman, Nachiketa, Anjan Dutt fall into this category of transition. Anjan, however, was least politically zealous among this trio, he could be said to be the first to welcome the rise of Bangla Bands.

Both Suman and Nachiketa have been close to different political formations at different points of time, but Anjan's separation from them is a significant factor, and he can be said to have formed a metatransitional phase within the songs of transition. He is in fact least convinced of political projects of change, and that betrays a postmodern non-commitment. Another important feature of these songs is that they are close to colloquial speech, unlike the songs of innocence, which very often used a flowery language. Indeed, the language of the songs of Shilajit, which comes into this category of transition

have been close to colloquial speech with a vengeance. His “Ghum Peyechhe Bari Ja” was a number that expressed anger at the diminishing prospect of a red morning (which means revolution), and asked the communist rulers (without directly taking their name) to go home as they are sleepy (Ghum Peyechhe Bari Ja). This was a vulgar and robust colloquialism, and this song became immensely popular.

Suman has collaborated with Anjan and Nachiketa at different points of his career. Left: an album made of live recording of Suman and Nachiketa together. Centre: an album of Suman (now Kabir) and Anjan together. Right: Suman and Anjan together in a live performance

Finally, what we (playfully again) call the songs of experience: they come with a postmodern (non)sensibility, with a project of decentring. Though they sometimes show a romantic nostalgia, and though they very often display an angst that emanates from a trapped existence, they do not hope for a redemption, or a possibility of turnaround and recovery. Songs of experience are sung by Bangla Bands like Fossils and Chandrabindoo. Singer-lyricist-composer Anupam Roy's works also come within this category. In fact, just the way Romantics were followed by Decadents in continental Europe in nineteenth century, in Bengali music, the long held dominion of a romantic sensibility (largely Tagore's creation, it did not exist in Kobigaan for example) finally gave way to a fractured, blasé (non)subjectivity depicted in these songs of experience.

Numerous other figures, singing sensations, popular musical formations and Bangla Bands have existed during this period, but this article will not deal with all of them, mostly because either their main characteristics are covered in our discussion, or because they often do not appear at the precise

Left: first album of Moheener Ghoraguli, 1977. Right: Comeback of Moheener Ghoraguli in 1995

junctions in the route of the trajectory we are mapping. Take for example the Bangla band Moheener Ghoraguli. Speaking of their time, they came much before the rise of Bangla Bands, much before even the emergence of Suman, and physically belonged to the late 1970s, only to re-emerge in mid-1990s. But a close investigation of Moheener Ghoraguli's lyrics will show that they belonged more to the category of songs of transition, their lyrics brimmed with some hopes for transformation or remembered those times too well when such transformations were possible, and unlike Chandrabindoo and Fossils did not have any project of decentring the subject of their songs. Another such time wrap would be Bhoomi. This Bangla band often betrays traits which are romantic, and their oeuvres can be categorised into songs of innocence. The resurgent film industry of Bengal in the new millennium has produced lyrics which are either superficially (or substantially) aligned with what we call the songs of experience, or are throwbacks of the previous phases.

Lastly, there is an obvious temptation to note that there is a broad decade-wise partition which corresponds with these three categories of Bengali music, as one phase is followed by the next: the first phase belonged to the 1980s, the second phase to the 1990s and the third phase to the 2000s and 2010s. This is just a broad correspondence. Songs of innocence continued to be produced throughout 1990s and 2000s (Manna Dey, Kumar Sanu, Amit Kumar continued to sing, for example) though the prime time was over by all means before the 1990s dawned in. Bangla Bands started emerging in the late 1990s, but they really happened big time after 2000. Suman-Nachiketa-Anjan continued to make songs well into 2000s, but their prime time was already over by 2000.

The unfortunate absence of any discussion on women (who have made it to popular Bengali music) in this article is apologised, and is attributable to the general male bias of the music industry. How many women composers or lyricists have been there, if we ask, we shall realise the lopsidedness of the situation, which in turn accounts for the lopsidedness of this article.

Manna Dey and Pulak Bandyopadhyay

Throughout the 1980s, until his demise in 1987, Kishore Kumar continued to deliver a number of popular songs, and was the strongest pillar of support to the Bengali music industry, film and non-film alike. Pulak Bandyopadhyay recollects many episodes from this period in his memoir, where Kishore recorded numerous hit film songs (159-168). Pulak Bandyopadhyay speaks of these songs, the tunes for most of which were composed by Ajay Das:

Pulak Bandyopadhyay with Kishore Kumar

Kishore Kumar in a live performance with Amit Kumar (left image) and Bappi Lahiri (image on right)

1. Hoyto Aamaake Karo Mone Nei
2. Aaj Milon Tithir Purnima Chaand
3. Ei To Eshechi Aami, Tomar Dadamoni
4. Onek Jomaano Byatha Bedona, Ki Kore Gaan Holo Jani Na
5. Aami Je Ke Tomar
6. Opaare Thaakbo Aami, Tumi Roibe Epaare
7. Aamaar E Kontho Bhore, Baaje Go Je Shur Baahaar
8. Mukhete Bolle Tumi Je Kotha
9. Chirodini Tumi Je Aamaar
10. Dujonaate Lekha Gaan, Bhenge Gaelo Bhul Shure
11. Bhalobasha Chara Aar Aache Ki
12. Notobor Nagor Tumi
13. Aamay Phuler Baagaan Diye Niye Jeo Na
14. Aamaroto Shaadh Chilo, Aasha Chhilo Mone
15. Bohu Dur Theke E Kotha
16. Tomaar Baarir Shaamne Diye Aamaar Moronjatra Jedin Jaabe

Pulak Bandyopadhyay speaks of each of these songs as an embedded memory, as an event, its recording and subsequent popular reception, but without mentioning their year of release, and without ordering them according to their time of release. Some of these songs belong to late 1970s, but most of them hail from the 1980s.

Arguably the most popular Bengali singer India ever witnessed till now is Kishore Kumar. We can agree that his voice and his style had a spontaneity (that's the main proposition of Derek Bose's study); Kishore's genius (for the absence of any other term) was unrestrained by grammar and training. Cinema finds it easier to subject its music to the expediency of script, commerce and, star system when it can have an impressive arsenal like Kishore. Just like capitalist modernity wants its human subjects to be autonomous, self-fashioning individuals who are uprooted from tradition and able to cope up with the challenges of the modern times, cinema has wanted the same from its music.

But for the same reason, music in modern age largely ceases to exist as a separate sphere independent of the socio-economic circumstances, subject to the iron rules of *gharana*, tradition and classical norms alone, which related to an aristocratic world order, and which thrived on patronage. As classical music gave way to popular music, as music commerce thrived, as new entertainment innovations like gramophone and talkies arrived, Bengalis increasingly started dominating the scenario in Bollywood as well as in Kolkata.

Classical music has always been submissive to the elites. Interestingly, the modern period is no different. Ajoy Chakraborty's book *Shrutinandan* (he runs an eponymous music school) is a testimony to his closeness to Jyoti Basu (whose letter of praise, following his visit to Chakraborty's music school is proudly reproduced in the book), and to Buddhadeb Bhattacharjee, Basu's main lieutenant and later Bengal's Chief Minister (whose numerous gestures of patronage are gratefully acknowledged). Chakraborty, after the regime change is heard to have formed closeness with the new party in power, a proof of which is that the artist has been generously awarded by Mamata Banerjee in recent years. This is by no means a commentary on any supposed expediency on the part of the said artist, or for that matter the ubiquitously politicised ambiance in which Bengalis have to breathe, but should be viewed as the genetic inability of classical music to exist without patronage. Not meant for popular consumption, classical music has to rely on elites. Derek Bose's study of Kishore Kumar on the other hand mentions an episode where Kishore flatly refused Sanjay Gandhi's request to sing at a function organised by the latter. This is where capitalism wins over feudalism, and popular music gains an upper score over classical music.

Ravishankar spoke very highly of two Bengali composers who dominated early film music in India during 1930s (we need to remember that film music did not arrive until the talkies), Raichad Boral and Pankaj Mullick, in his autobiography *Raag Onuraag* (172, 175-6). One major reason why

they succeeded, as the present writer would suggest, was that they had an unorthodox (as opposed to classicist) approach to music, a strong tendency to experiment, and an attitude of openness to the varieties of music from different parts of India and the world, and these are precisely what this new art form of cinema required. Tagore's compositions in this respect probably acted as a precedent, which allowed Bengali composers of film music to be malleable and multi-faceted, versatile and variegated, experimental and engaging. Bengalis dominated popular music industry from Kolkata to Mumbai, and the reason lies in Bengal's musical adaptability. Perhaps, one can go back beyond Tagore and trace in the genre of Kobigaan these particular traits which have allowed Bengalis to be successful in the field of film music.

However, the new art form of film music did not just require openness, it required rigour and demanded discipline too. Pulak Bandyopadhyay informs us about the rpm (revolutions per minute) economy which commanded the physical shape of popular music. Bandyopadhyay in the very beginning of his memoir *Kothay Kothay Raat Hoye Jaay* mentions that during the days of gramophone records, a disc record had the duration of three minutes and ten seconds, which had to be the length of a song (and the lyricist and composer and singer had to act accordingly) (7). Undoubtedly, film music, as it too had to be released on disc records, had to work within that restraint. Economy of long playing records (generally two songs on each side) later gave way to audio cassettes (six songs on each side), which meant that the production line had to enlarge itself. Bengalis who have dominated music industry responded with a prolific output.

It should be mentioned that Bengali composers did not just dominate Bollywood, but also had a sizeable international clout, Ravishankar himself being an example of that. Udayshankar's close aide, Timirbaran Bhattacharya, who was an internationally acclaimed Sarod player is another example of Bengali composers making it big abroad. He became a famous music director in the Pakistani film industry centred in Karachi.

As we get to see that Bengali dominance continued in Bollywood well into the 1940s, 1950s, 1960s, we need to remember that the likes of Raichand Boral and Pankaj Mullick worked in an atmosphere quite different from the one in which K C Dey and S D Burman and Salil Chowdhury dominated Bombay industry, as the second group was constituted by migrants/refugees from a stagnant Bengali industry. Therefore, the Bengali dominance in the film music of Bombay industry also signifies a Brain drain, as it comes to signify a cultural imperialism to which Kolkata's music industry was

subjected to. But that was perhaps still qualitatively better than the ghastly sway of southern dominance over Bengali industry of today

This should also be noted that cinema as an industry not just subjects music to the vagaries of market, to the whims of consumer preference and to the unscrupulous money that oils this giant wheel, but makes music a truly public, collaborative art form. However, precedents always existed in the forms of popular performances of *Kirton*, *Kobigaan*, *Jatra*, from which the musical unconscious of Indian and Bengali cinema continued to draw its paradigms. But it rarely so happened that the famous trinity of lyricist, composer and singer came to be fused into a unitary godhead, when it came to film music. Still, such a unitary trend exists from Tagore to Kabir Suman, representing an underlying current of romantic individualism which also impregnates the idea of autonomous self-fashioning.

Some albums of Suman Chattopadhyay

It's not like film music as a form of collaboration deliberately stayed away from that individualistic subjective pattern, but no doubt film music encourages popular, public stereotypes as opposed to subjective extremities. The decline of Bengali film music towards the end of 1980s created the scope for the emergence of unitary music, which fused the lyricist, composer and singer into one figure again, as Suman Chatterjee burst into the scenario. For someone who was growing up during the 1980s and 1990s, which is the case of the present writer, there was a paradigm shift when singers like Suman and Nachiketa arrived.

Again, it was not exactly that Bengali music completely crashed and came to a standstill before their arrival, which is how popular perception frequently puts it. The truth is in fact far from that. But there is no denying that a new development was taking place in the early 1990s.

Actually, Bengali music became closer to contemporary sensibility in the 1990s with the advent of Suman Chattopadhyay. In his autobiography Suman speaks of the separation of Bengali songs from the colloquial, contemporary, modern language of Bengali poetry (177), and speaks of his resolve to write such lyrics which will not be susceptible to such admixture of *shadhu* and *cholit* (a grammatical vice called *guruchondali*, which has long been banned in prose, but curiously continued to appear in popular song lyrics). It should be noted here that the songs of experience, as we are calling them, have been painstakingly aware of the question of modernisation and standardisation of Bengali words, and Rupam Islam devotes a number of pages to this question in *Rupam on the Rocks* and informs us that his concern with modernisation of spelling goes back to his little magazine days (93-97).

Rupam Islam's first book (Rock journal to be precise), *Rupam on the Rocks*, which was also the name of a popular fm radio programme that Rupam Islam did

When it comes to the Bangla Band Chandrabindoo, it is interesting to note that their three figureheads, even after the band has virtually stopped to bring out its own albums, continue to work as journalists. Chandril and Anindya have long stints as journalists. Anindya at present edits the Sunday magazine *Robbar* from the house of *Protidin*, and Chandril, having worked in the ABP group, which was followed by a period of separation during which he worked in *Robbar* is now again associated with ABP group. Upal, in his capacity as a cartoonist is also associated with ABP group.

Chandrabindoo. Upal in the centre, Chandril on extreme right, Anindya on extreme left.

Chandril has two books of poems to his credit till date, and he was a student of SRFTI, the only film school of Kolkata could boast of for a long time. The present writer had the opportunity to watch Chandril's diploma film, *Y2K- Sex Krome Aashitechhe*. Throughout his writings, be it lyric, poem, or prose, Chandril strategically uses sexuality to frequently undercut romantic notions of love. More importantly Chandril's non-fictional prose has been a trendsetter in Bengali language, and his writing style has been numerously replicated from big media houses to little magazines. Frequent puns, neologism, parody, pastiche of history and culture, defamiliarising perspectives on current affairs, a (non)belief in the ubiquity of human drudgery, dreadfulness, and death, a decentred and decadent (non)subjectivity mark the content of his prose, while the form is likewise fractured, punctured and sentences often run into several lines without full stop, with a heavy use of comma. They form a community with the lyrics of Chandrabindoo, which very often have a deliberately anarchic quality, and resist all stable, assured grand narratives.

Some of the albums of Chandrabindoo

No wonder that Chandrabindoo turned the slogan of Nabarun Bhattacharya's *fyatarus* into music (fyat fyat shai shai), which was also used in the eponymous play of Suman Mukhopadhyay. The blurb of *Rosh Kosh Shingara Bulbuli Mostok* (collection of Chandril's writings published in *ABP*) introduces Chandril as a non-doer of a series of non-deeds, like he did not refuse a million dollar prize, did not inhabit an asylum after a melancholic breakdown, and that includes this description: he did not read Baudrillard. Such a negative mention of this renowned postmodern thinker is in agreement with the style of postmodern literature.

Anindya began his career as a trainee journalist in the newly revived news daily *Jugantar* in 1993, which very soon closed down again. His regular column in *Robbar* titled *Niruddesh Shomporke Ghoshona* (Declaration about the Missing), later published as an eponymous book, had one entry on this episode of his life (36-41). The same book of Anindya curiously also has an article on Suman Chattopadhyay. Given that this book deals only with the missing (The book opens with an article on Dodo birds, ends with one on Neandarthals, and also has an entry on Soviet Union), this topic is interesting. At an obvious level, following his conversion, Suman Chattopadhyay really ceased to exist, and was replaced by Kabir Suman. But at another level, when Anindya was writing this column, Suman ceased to exist as a musical phenomenon, and became rather known for his politics. Still, it is imperative on us to note how Anindya describes the rise of Suman:

In the beginning of the 1990s, there was not anything special in Bengal's bazaar. Neither any political movement, nor any great socio-event, even the excitement of Mohunbagan and East Bengal did not at all stir us then. People used to silently watch One Day Cricket matches on colour television and noisily watch theatre at Academy. Politics and sexuality both were so very drab that (a rally at) Brigade or (Raaga) Bidhushri no longer appealed to the Bengali mind. Even the biggest chicken did not ever think that the Marxist Communist Party's government would lay an egg of people's democratic revolution one day. Barring some vegetarian stains of piss, nothing was written on discoloured walls.

In that middle-classiness Suman comes. As the embodiment of Grim Reaper (Kalbhoirob). As the dream, hope and wish fulfilment of a whole generation. (18-19)

It can surely be said that Suman's advent brought Bengali song closer to Bengali poetry that has been written in an urban, smart, contemporary language (as I observed in my article on Ishwarchandra Gupta

in JBS 3.2, this is not merely a twentieth century phenomenon, and can be said to be largely a legacy of Ishwar Gupta). More importantly, Suman's oeuvre brought Bengali music into a community with Bengali literature. Songs again regained that literary respectability which was lost after Tagore, to the point that lines from Suman's song “Shurjo Bollo Ish” from his second album *Boshe Aanko* appeared in the Bengali question paper of the Test Examination of Madhyamik at Hindu School, Kolkata in 1995, as the present writer remembers having seen it in the proverbial and iconic *Test Papers* published by ABTA (All Bengal Teachers' Association) in 1996 (it came in the *Bhaab Shomprosharon* or expand-the-theme segment).

Suman's writing career (that was journalistic in nature, where he used the pen name Manab Mitra) in fact preceded his emergence as a popular singer during 1990s, a fact which is put forward in his autobiography. Quite interestingly, Nachiketa too is a writer, and has a collection of his writings published from Patra Bharati Kolkata. Apart from contributing occasional columns to newspapers, he has authored stories and novels. Many of them harbour an angst that emerges from the failure of the communist project of revolution in Bengal (Nachiketa's songs “Anirban” and “Anirban 2” immediately coming to mind, which speak of a Naxalite revolutionary named Anirban). Some of them display the contemporary quagmire of deceit, political ploys, helplessness of people, corruption, an overall social inertia, and in the midst of this murky atmosphere, rise of a hero who is unmistakably an image of Nachiketa himself. The details of the fictions are not so much important. What is more to the point here is that Nachiketa's fiction writing forms a community with his music; his fictions connect his songs to others cultural forms.

Nachiketa's first three albums, in that order

Anjan Dutt was primarily into cinema before he came to be a lyricist-composer-singer. He got best actor award for his role in the film *Chaalchitra* in the Venice Film Festival in 1981, which was more than a decade before his first music album was released. His experience of his first movie as a director, *Badadin* (1998) got reflected in his song “Raja Ray” from mid-1990s. That song also spoke about the despondent situation of contemporary Bengali film industry. Dutt directed his next movie *Bow Barracks Forever* in 2004, and since then has done very few music albums, and been into film direction (occasional acting too) mostly.

Throughout the 1990s what (again by popular perception) was called Jibonmukhi songs (the epithet Jibonmukhi, first used by Nachiketa in his first album – the cover of the first album prominently declared itself as “Jibonmukhi Bangla Gan”, like Suman's albums used to have the heading Sumoner gaan in the beginning) dominated music industry, and as a result, what existed prior to that became obscure, and rapidly went on to become passe, at least among the youth.

Kishore's death led to the rise of Kumar Sanu, a shadow singer who used to imitate Kishore. Indeed the very first album of Sanu, *Amar Shilpi*, was a tribute to Kishore Kumar after his death. The lasting popularity of these albums, originally released in cassette format during late 1980s, ensured that they were later released in CD format as well, during the 1990s

However, no one can forget the tremendous popularity of Kumar Sanu (lampooned as Kumar Panu in one of the popular numbers composed and sung by Nachiketa, titled “Ulto Rajar Deshe”) music towards the end of 1980s and early 1990s. He gave three phenomenal hits in rapid succession: Omor Shilpi, Shurer Rojonigondha and Priyotoma Mone Rekho. Kumar Sanu, originally named Kedar Bhattacharya, was a known shadow singer who sang the songs of Kishore Kumar, and Sanu's rise itself was made possible by the demise of Kishore Kumar. To the credit of Kumar Sanu, we must admit that the songs had melodious tunes, had tolerably good lyrics, and Sanu's vocal rendition had a quality which could appeal to the masses.

These albums mostly used to be released before DurgaPujo. Being non-film music, their release was strategically done at this point, as Bengalis purchased Pujor Gaan since music industry emerged in Bengal, and that goes back to the days of Gramophone. When DurgaPujo came, such songs, played on loudspeakers at different *Pujo Mondops* (Makeshift Canopies which act as temple of Goddess Durga for the period of DurgaPujo) used to generate a festive ambience.

When Kumar Sanu was singing “amar shohor Kolkata” (Kolkata my city), a popular number from his repertory from late 1980s, there was a distinctly leftist-sounding chorus playing in the background. Of course that does not mean such *oposhongshkriti* (literally meaning bad culture, a bhadrakok concept used to distinguish approved, sombre and respectable forms of culture from non-approved, non-sombre, non-respectable forms of culture) as Kumar Sanu had no easy acceptance in the respectable and conservative plethora of certified bhadrakok culture. Further, songs of movies like *Beder Meye Jyotsna* (a Bangladesh-inspired film, songs of which were sung by Kumar Sanu) enjoyed a certain immunity from the left, as they were too embarrassing even to discuss.

Anjan Dutt in one of his early songs addressed to Suman comes up with this line “Robindro Ki Gonoshongeet konotai thik dicchilo na buker bhetor phNushe othar rosh” (Neither Tagore songs, nor people's songs provided the angst that one needs in the bosom to speak out), which neatly sums up the musical preference of the bhadrakoks prior to the songs of transition. People's songs (gonoshongeet) was the standard name applied to leftist songs, alluding to a sustained cultural phenomenon that began with Gononatyo Songho (IPTA). Significantly, Anjan always acknowledged Suman as the fountainhead of the kind of songs he himself believed in doing. Indeed, Suman spearheaded this kind of ideological constellation within which Anjan's songs moved, which was progressive, liberal, humanist, universalist and hopeful of change. The title song of one of Anjan's albums says: *Cholo Bodlai* (Let's Change).

Dutta's first album, *Shunte Ki Chao* and second album, *Purono Guita*

Remake of popular film (and non-film) songs from the black and white era shot to prominence, albeit briefly, during 1990s. Srikanto Acharjee is generally considered to be the most popular singer associated with this phenomenon of remake, though he later on himself gave up remaking, and instead concentrated on his own basic songs. A testimony to barren times, when left platitudes replaced experiment and innovation in popular culture, this remake phenomenon also touches upon the commerce of live shows which form the bread and butter of singers, and which generally have a steady demand for the popular songs of yesteryears. Remake thus connected music commerce directly with the culture of soirees and performances. Remake was also a crucial expression of the widespread cultural phenomenon of shadow singing. As the songs of transition were not best known for melody, the phenomenon of remake also filled a certain vacuum, a demand for melody that was not catered to by Suman, Nachiketa and Anjan.

The rapid rise and fall of CDs have been followed by a return of film music in Bengal. Commerce dictates that music finds it easier to survive in live concerts and in the promotional campaigns of film music, in this age of internet piracy. Anupam Roy's arrival marks this significant

new turn in the trajectory of Bengali popular music. Chandrabindoo started their foray into Bengali film music in 2009, and till 2012, they worked as lyricist, music composer and vocalist in a number of movies. For the movie *Antaheen*, they won national award for best lyrics in 2010 (the movie was released in 2009). However, after 2012, they have no significant movie to their credit, and this probably alludes to a waning of Chandrabindoo's influence after the arrival of Anupam Roy (both have the same target audience, hence a competition cannot be ruled out). Between 2009 and 2012, members of Chandrabindoo have lent their music, lyric and voice to these movies: *Box No 1313*, *Cross Connection*, *Brake Fail*, *Antaheen* (all 2009 movies), *Jodi Ekdin*, *Ekti Tarar Khonje*, *033*, *Natobar Not Out* (all 2010 movies), *Icche*, *Rang Milanti*, *Gosainbaganer Bhoot* (all 2011 movies), *Aparajita Tumi* (2012).

Chandrabindoo won national award for best lyrics for the movie *Antaheen*

During this phase, Kabir Suman himself increasingly started acting in films, and working as composer-lyricist-singer in film music. He has acted in all the movies of director Suman Mukhopadhyay till now. He also bagged national award for music direction in 2014 for Srijit Mukherjee's *Jatismar*.

A Poster of the movie Jatishmar

Back in 1990s, Nachiketa gave music to a soap opera, titled *Kuasha Jokhon* and the music became hugely popular following which the songs of that daily soap (in Tollygunge lingo, megaserial) were commercially released in an eponymous album.

Nachiketa's album *Kuasha Jokhon*

Rupam Islam received national award for playback singing in *Mahanagar@Kolkata* in 2010. Rupam directed the music of this movie as well.

A Poster of Mahanagar@Kolkata

Anupam Roy's first solo album (2012) comes two years after his successful stint in film music. His songs in *Autograph* in 2010 catapulted him to tremendous fame, and in 2015, he has made his debut in Bollywood with the film *Piku*.

Between 2010 and 2015, Anupam Roy has been associated with these movies as vocalist/lyricist/composer:

2010: *Autograph*

2011: *Cholo Paltai, Rong Milanti, Baishe Sraon*

2012: *One Liner, Teen Yaari Kotha, Hemlock Society, Laptop, Chorabali*

2013: *Shunyo Onko*

2014: *Chhaya Manush, Window Connection, Highway, Chotushkone*

2015: *Bela Sheshe, Piku (Hindi), Kath Mundu, Saheb Bibi Golam*

Three Albums of Anupam Roy: *Bakyobageesh*, *Durbane Chokh Rakhbo Na*, *Dwitiyo Purush*

Besides, Roy has worked in 22 Bengali movies in the capacity of a vocalist for other lyricists and composers so far. He has been associated with little magazines, has published two books of poems. He got his first novel published in 2014, and in 2015 made his foray into Bengali graphic novel. In autograph, his song “Aamake Amar Moto Thakte Dao” has a line: “amar jonno aalo jelo na keu” (nobody put up a light for me). Such a renegade line was not possible in the earlier two phases.

Here, let us reassert that in the journey from the songs of innocence to those of transition, subjectification undergoes certain shifts towards an urban, bhadrak, left-liberal paradigm; but those changes notwithstanding, there is no fundamental transformation of the mode of subjectivity. The same individualism, the same naivety, same positivism, the same high Romantic-Victorian sensibility (that witnesses its Bengali apogee in Tagore) are frequently seen. Until the songs of experience arrive on the scenario, the feminine subject (the love interest) is what the author makes her to be, in the vein of “Amaro Porano Jaha Chay, Tumi Tai Go”.

Suman reflects this pattern of subjectivity when he says in “Tomake Chai”, that he wants to behold his beloved bringing festive spirit to a rally of tired people. However, in the song “Office Time” (from the album *Ar Jani Na*, later on remade as the album *Ebhabeo Phire Aasha Jaay*) of Chandrabindoo, the lyric says that there is no chance that she would be found in a rally (“Michhile Tomake Dekhte Pawar Kono Scene-ee Nei”). From the subject of modernity, to the non-subject of postmodernity, if we trace this development in Bengali popular music, the first thing that strikes us is that *Ar Jani Na* was released in 1997, while *Tomake Chai* came in 1991. It can be said that within a period of six years, Bengali music moved from modernism to postmodernism, from live-giving illusions to disillusionment.

There are reasons to classify Band music as postmodern. It is less self-assured, more decentred. It does not speak of revolutionary resistance in the vein of a Suman or Nachiketa, but instead reveals a blasé knowledgeable about the present condition. The non-subject, with all the angst and entrapment of existence becomes a recurrent trope in Rupam Islam's music. Again it is significant that Rupam started his musical career after his foray into little magazines (*Ei To Aami* 126-7). Rupam in fact in his high school days founded an organisation called Avant Garde Parishad (Parishad is Bengali for Council), and as the name suggests, they discussed the latest intellectual trends from the west. The little magazine edited by Rupam was the mouthpiece of this organisation.

Cover of Ei To Ami

Cover of Rockstar

Rupam in spite of having a predominant image as a solitary singer – indeed he has solo albums to his credit – has always stuck to the band format for public performances. His music can be said to exist in a community. His mention of his closeness to late poet Sunil Ganguly (*Rockstar 7*), among other things, alludes to the fact that his lyrics exist in a cultural continuum with Bengali poetry. Further, he looks at the band music as partnership, as a collaborative project; however, he sees lyric writing as an essentially solitary endeavour (speaks of the necessity of creative loneliness), which must be shaded from the glare of the collective (*Rockstar 26-27*).

Some of the solo albums of Rupam Islam

Bangla Bands' music is known for its peppy, popular, fast rhythmic tunes, but fast tunes earmarked our folk songs for a very long time. Kobiwalas used to have a repertory of both slow melody and fast rhythm. While the first appealed to the elites, the latter was a favourite of toiling masses, and for further details, one can refer to my article in the previous issue of *Journal of Bengali Studies* Vol.3, No.2.

Shiva's songs can be taken for an example: be it the high Sanskrit Shiva tandava stotram, or colloquial Shiber gajon, they always display a festive pace, a rapid flow of rhythm.

Going back to Suman's songs, we can say that if that music lacked a popular vigour and fast rhythm, that lacking was probably attributable to the left-liberal bhadrakal tastes which dominated the social reception of art. Suman's autobiography is a case in point.

A Sharodiya Pujoshonkha is a complete configuration of space and time. In a periodical, the political infrastructure of a period's culture is laid bare as if in a Brechtian theatre. The Pujoshonkha of Aajkaal in the Bengali year 1400 (1993 CE) exemplarily illustrates this aspect. Suman Chattopadhyay authored his memoir *Hoye Otha Gaan* (Song Being Made) in this pujoshonkha. The editorial of this issue expresses remorse over the demise of Utpal Dutt, and this pujoshonkha pays homage to him by posthumously publishing his play “Ognishojja” (Bed of Fire) which is a tirade against Hindu fundamentalism in the backdrop of Raja Rammohan Roy's movement against Sati immolation. The play begins with a snide attack against Ayurveda (identified with quackery) with which the western system of medicine is then favourably compared. Hinduism is depicted in a completely negative light, collaboration with the west is promoted in the guise of bishshomanobota. The same pujoshonkha carried a novel by Debesh Roy on the demolition of Babri Mosque.

Suman in an interview, back in 1990s

This was the political climate prevailing in the early 1990s which saw the advent of Suman Chatterjee's music. Suman, in the title song of his third album, *Icehe Holo*, observes that he wants to see collective farming all over the world before he breathes his last (“Morbo Dekhe Bishshojure

Jouthokhamar”). That aspiration, and that potential hope (the album was released in 1993) constituted the core leftist ethos which permeated this milieu from which Suman's songs emerged. Contrary to that, Rupam Islam's song “Ei To Ami” in *Mahanagar@Kolkata* says “Ei To Amar/Jouthokhamar/Katchhi Katbo/Shesh Phoshol/Boshundhora/Ghater Mora/Chitar Kathe/Shoinyodol” (This is my collective farm, I reap and shall reap the last harvest, this earth is moribund, and the soldiers are on the burning pyre of woods). Collective farming, which stood for a promise of life in death, in fact, nothing short of resurrection in Suman's lyric, comes to signify a lone reaper of the last harvest from an earth that is morbid, and there is an imagery of death in fire with no possibility of resurrection (because the pagan pyre, unlike the Judeo-Christian-Islamic tomb, does not speak of resurrection, immortality of the soul notwithstanding).

Suman's songs were markedly different in one respect from the kind of music which previously dominated our popular sensibility, as we already pointed out: his songs lacked melody. They also had a discernible western influence, which was also true (to a greater degree) about Anjan Dutt who soon followed Suman. It is interesting that there is at least one western song which had been rendered separately by Suman and Anjan into Bengali. Anjan's “Ekta Bondhu Hobe Ki Bolo Tumi Amar” and Suman's “Chaichi Tomar Bondhuta” both are direct Bengali renderings of a song of Bob Dylan; the tunes are different, and the adapted lyrics are at slight variance too, but the Dylan stamp is unmistakable. Suman's Bengali songs have been variously derived from the west, Dylan's “Blowin' in the Wind” has become “Kotota Poth Perole” for example. He has been called Bengal's Bob Dylan, a tag which came probably because he sang with a guitar on the stage, and was as such the first known Bengali singer to have done so, and it was a tag that he refused. Nevertheless, Suman's autobiography *Hoye Otha Gaan* is a testimony to the thorough western influence on his music, his childhood training in Indian classical notwithstanding (though he was exposed to a variety of western music from his childhood because of his musician parents).

Death of the author used to imply the death of the romantic dream of the individualist-solitary author. However, in our academia, this concept was used to peddle an ahistorical view of the text: death of the author meant death of history, and everyone was free to interpret a text as an autonomous, self-fashioning unit following I A Richards and F R Leavis. This was actually a backdoor return of the individual author, only the author got rechristened as a close text, without any context whatsoever. As we look at the concept of *auteur* in cinema studies, we find that usual high romantic emphasis on the

singularity, solitariness of a self-fashioning individual work. Now, Bengali songs since the lyrical revolution staged by Tagore, entered this ahistorical phase. As opposed to that, Kobigaan was deeply immersed in history. Vaishnav songs operated within a hermeneutics of myth and history. Songs were part of a larger network.

It is a folk Indian tradition that gives birth to our film music (deriving from our age old cultural repertory of *jatra*; in north India it went by the name of *nautanki*; all of them go back to the high position assigned to music in dramatic performances in Sanskrit, Pali and Prakrit), and therefore songs and dance in our cinema have a historical context.

When Suman appears on the musical scene, he represents a curious admixture of this culture industry. On one hand, he is a lone auteur, a self-fashioning bhadralok, representing the high individualist dream of a Tagoeran sensibility, on the other hand, he made songs which clearly acknowledged a social and political matrix within which the verbal machinery operated. But ironically, rise of Suman also registers the fatal break-up of bhadralok and popular culture. Pulak Bandyopadhyay sometime in the 1990s complained in an interview (no citation can be given, as it was an interview in an obsolete film magazine from the Aajkaal group, titled *Television* that later stopped circulation; the present writer refers to it from memory, as no copy of the magazine could be procured) that producers insisted that Bengali movies are seen by rickshaw pullers, and songs should be meant for them, lyric should be what they could understand. This tension did not exist earlier. As Bengali music veered towards the Songs of experience, the single screen theatres gave way to multiplexes, which simply resolved this problem by making niche movies, targeted at urban middle classes.

When Trinomool Congress was formed in 1998, the first visible political spectacle was the so-called “Cut-out culture” imported from the south of India. Large cut out images of Trinomool supremo flooded the roads of Kolkata. Interestingly, it was the same period when Bengali film industry was beginning to get influenced by South, which could of course be a mere case of coincidence, but probably Bengal badly needed some blood transfusion, no matter whatever was the quality of the blood. The influence was discernible in the case of Film music. “O Bondhu Tumi Shunte Ki Pao, Ei Gaan Aamaar” (Hey Friend, Can You Hear This Song of Mine), a chartbuster from the first commercially successful movie of Superstar Jeet (*Shaathi*), was a case in point. The tune of typically south, vocal rendition was characteristically southern, the first part of the opening was sung in a doleful melody (“O Bondhu Tumi Shunte Ki Pao) followed by a peppy rhythm (“Ei Gaan Aamaar”). It was a turnaround of sorts for an

industry which many observers viewed as sick; after almost a decade a Bengali film song was doing the rounds in DurgaPujo loudspeakers everywhere.

This is not to say that Bengali film music since the talkies used to exist in a pristine state prior to the recent southern turn. It was always influenced by external factors. Western influences have always been there. Then, with the great slump followed by the closing down of New Theatres and the mass exodus of Bengali film artists to Bombay, in a classic case of Derridean supplementarity, credit titles in the beginning of a movie began showing the suffix Bombay within a bracket after the name of an artist; this is, for example, how Manna Dey sang his first Bengali film song. It carried weight, commanded awe, guaranteed commercial appeal, and ensured that the Bengali film industry is forever enthralled to the glamorous dominance of Bollywood. And this is how Bengali popular music was surviving throughout the 1980s.

In this scenario, Suman's advent was like arrival of fresh rain in the midst of an excruciating Indian summer. The later phenomenon of Bangla Bands and the arrival of Anupam Roy cannot ever be sufficiently grateful to Suman, for this single reason, that in Suman Chattopadhyay, Bengal attained musical sovereignty after a long time, as it stopped being subjected to the ignominy of being a satellite of Bollywood and other non-Bengali power centres. However, this sovereignty ever since is repeatedly corroded as we lack a consolidated Bengali capitalist class who can promote and produce cinema and other allied public arts like the music industry. In a classic illustration of Marxian base-superstructure model, the crisis of Bengali music emanates from the crisis of Bengali economy.

In spite of that crisis, there is much in the achievement of Bengali music in the recent decades which can be celebrated. The richness and variety of its development can be a treasure island for cultural studies. Its trajectory has interesting turns. The songs of innocence had a belief that love was possible, the songs of transition had a belief that revolution was possible, but the songs of experience have this (non)belief that love and revolution are perennially deferred and remain illusively out of reach. The first category was mostly sentimental, conformist and commercial, the second was mostly sassy, candid and conscientious, the third continues to be savvy, non-credulous, non-committed and nonchalant. For a cultural historian, these three phases of Bengali music can map the social, political and cultural evolution of the Bengali people throughout the 1980s, 1990s, 2000s and 2010s.

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